

A NOVEL INJECTION PROCESS FOR LONG FIBER COMPOSITES USING ROTATION

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Keywords: *centrifugal forces, non-rotational-symmetric parts, off-axis injection, air separation device, process technology*

Abstract

A recently-developed process to manufacture composite parts is described. The injection pressure is applied via centrifugal forces. The physical effects of rotation are arranged for both achieving very high injection rates compared to the RTM process and separating the embedded air from the matrix system. Pump technologies are not needed. The manufactured CFRP parts own a high fiber volume and low porosity content. The results promise an integration of this manufacturing technique in the industrial process chain.

1. Introduction

The trend to high production volume and therefore further automated processes for composite structures leads to a great demand for methods to reduce the infusion and curing time. State-of-the-art processes such as “the resin infusion under flexible tooling process” (RIFT) and the “resin transfer molding process” (RTM) have restrictions. While the cost-efficient RIFT process is unsuitable for high volume production of composite parts, the cost-intensive RTM process is limited by infiltration effects like fiber washing and increasing equipment costs.

To solve this contradiction centrifugal forces are introduced to generate the necessary pressure difference to transfer the resin to the cavity.

In contrast to familiar techniques of producing composite structures via rotational devices [1-4], structures which are not rotation-symmetric can be produced. The process discussed here enables very high pressure loads while the fibers remain in their original position based on the compaction of the preform through centrifugal forces.

This paper presents the basic method, the physical principle, the experimental set-up and the test procedure for the process. As basic test geometry a plate measuring 300 mm x 200 mm x 4mm is chosen. Non-crimp glass and carbon fiber fabrics are injected with matrix systems of various viscosities. Different matrix systems and process parameters are used to verify the process. The quality of the components produced with this method is evaluated. Finally, the economic potentials and challenges of the process concerning the prevailing process chain of composite materials are discussed.

2. Method

Centrifugal forces are used to generate the necessary pressure difference to transfer the matrix material to dry fiber structure.

2.1 General

The dry preform is placed at a defined distance from the axis of rotation and is rotated around the central axis (*Fig. 1*). A matrix system is

installed on the tooling side situated closer to the axis of rotation. The force induced during rotation affects the resin system and the fiber material. In placing an extra mass on top of the resin the generated pressure difference can be adjusted. (Fig. 2) Accordingly, the dry fiber material is filled with resin. Using the principle of a centrifuge, the fluids, in the form of resin and air, can be separated. Therefore, holes are located on the inside of the tooling. In addition, the preform is compacted during the rotation process.

Fig. 1: Principle of the off-axis rotational device.

In Fig. 2 two various modified composite built-ups are depicted. The rotational off-axis injection process can be generated with a RIFT or with a RTM-tool as it is done in the following.

Fig. 2: Two various modified composite built-ups: RIFT (left); RTM (right).

The characteristics of the discussed method compared to traditional methods are:

a) State-of-the-art RTM processes for high volume of production are limited to a maximum injection pressure of approx. 60 - 100 bar due to fiber washing and increasing equipment costs. Fiber washing (displacement of the fiber material in the mold during the injection process) was shown to be a problem at static RTM processes using high pressure rates. The idea is to establish an alternative manufacturing technique to the common RTM systems engineering through a rotational device.

The physical effects of this novel method gain very high injection pressure rates with little operating expense. The LCC demonstrator ROTAC has the potential to produce 70-130bar without any pump technologies. (Fig. 3) Applications for the industrial use can easily be scaled to achieve even higher pressures.

b) Use of good-natured, high-viscosity matrix systems: There has always been a trade-off between a short injection time and a short curing time. Highly automated composite manufacturing processes use low-viscosity matrix systems which have on the one hand side the advantage that it can be injected easily and quickly. On the other hand low-viscosity systems exceed a high rate of exotherm energy during curing and have little operation time in general. Process which can apply high pressure rates can purpose the user to use high-viscosity matrix systems. The high pressure may allow the first-ever infiltration of thermoplastic matrix systems.

c) The dry preform is compacted through the rotational forces. Though this additional compacting forces the fiber washing effects are minimized.

d) The principle of a centrifuge separates embedded air from the matrix system. While the matrix will remain in the closed mold, the air

can exhaust through holes inserted in the inner tooling. No previous outgassing of the mixed resin has to be conducted. Hence, the process steps separating of the embedded air in the mixed resin and the venting of the tooling's cavity can be dropped. No excess matrix material exhausts while this happens at RIFT and RTM due to the fact that an almost void-free composite part is aimed.

2.2 Physical effects

The rotation induces two principle physical effects: centrifugal forces to inject the applied matrix system and the sedimentation velocity for the separation processes of embedded air in the matrix system:

2.2.1 Centrifugal forces

Due to the rotation the matrix system and fiber material is exposed to an angular velocity (ω) according to (1):

$$\omega = d\phi/dt. \quad (1)$$

The centrifugal forces (F_z) affect the fiber material, the resin material and the imposed mass (m). These are dependent on the distance (r) from the center of rotation to each component of the system:

$$F_z = m \cdot \omega^2 \cdot r = m \cdot v^2 / r. \quad (2)$$

The resin is introduced into the closed mold via a pin gate. The pressure of injection can be simply calculated.

Fig. 3: Plot of injection pressure against frequency of rotation.

2.2.2 Sedimentation velocity

The sedimentation velocity (3) is the velocity which molecules move in response to centrifugal forces generated in a centrifuge. The embedded air moves in the direction of the rotational axis till it exhausts through the holes on the inner tooling to the environment.

$$v_s = (m \cdot r \cdot \omega^2) / 6 \cdot \pi \cdot \eta \cdot r_0 \quad (3)$$

- v_s : sedimentation speed
- m : mass of void
- r_0 : radius of void
- r : distance between void and rotation axis
- η : viscosity of the matrix system

The sedimentation velocity through centrifugal forces is used to determine the process time and rotational speed that is required to separate embedded air from the matrix system.

3. Experimental approach

A demonstrator ROTAC was developed and is allocated in the LCC-facilities to investigate the rotation injection process. [5] The primary aim of the demonstrator is a) to verify the principles of the injection process by varying process parameters and material systems, b) to demonstrate the separation principle between

embedded air and matrix material and c) to study the influence of different matrix systems. A qualitative material characterization by means of fiber volume content and porosity is conducted to compare the material properties to common manufacturing techniques. The test samples are an indicator for the feasibility of manufacturing composite parts and the potentials of integration in the composite manufacturing process chain. (*chap. 5*)

3.1 Demonstrator

The test facility can be operated up to 5 rounds per second. The rotational speed can be programmed and controlled with an external PC-software. The 2.2kW motor actuates an axle which is attached to the body through a fixed/moveable bearing. The closed tool is fixed off-axis. On the opposite side a corresponding counterbalance is mounted. Imbalances during the rotation are absorbed through dampers at the floor.

Fig. 4: Demonstrator ROTAC.

3.2 Test procedure

The tool (*Fig. 4, left*) is prepared outside of the rotational device for the injection. Cleaning, application of the release agent, the layup/insertion of the dry preform, etc. are done at a separate table. The mold is clothed and fixed by screws. The matrix system is provided

in a plastic bag and applied in the fixture. The tool is then assembled into the rotational device. (*Fig.4, right*) The tool is rotated till the resin exceeds at the four holes of the outgassing device. After the injection through rotation the saturated mold is removed from the device again and cured in the oven. The pin gate and the outgassing holes are sealed.

4. Results

A preform made of glass fibers (S32EX010, Saertex GmbH & Co. KG) is injected with two various resin systems. First the matrix system (RIM135 / RIMH1366, Momentive) with a viscosity of about 400mPas at 20°C was injected at RT=18°C. CR141 (SIKA GmbH) is a matrix system which was basically developed for filament wind processes due to its high-viscosity (600mPas at T=25°C). This matrix system is successfully used for the injection of a glass fiber preform through rotation at RT. A carbon fiber preform (SIGRATEX® HPT, SGL Group) is injected.

Microscopic observations show an overall high compaction rate. (*Fig. 5*) The laminate which is located closer to the rotation axis owns a higher content of porosity than the outer laminate. This may be a first evidence of the principle “sedimentation”. (see *chap. 2.2.2*) The laminate in the area of the central pin gate shows a good laminate quality in form of a low void content. The porosity level is increasing with the distance to the pin gate.

Fig. 5: Through-thickness section of an injected and cured GFRP plate.

5. Discussion

A potential industrial process chain and a feasibility study are discussed.

5.1. Potential industrial process chain

The centrifugal method for the production of composite parts enables the possibility to separate the filling process from the curing process. One possible and potential scenario of process steps is shown in *Fig. 6*. The device may comprise several fixtures for multiple tools. After the preform has been filled with resin by rotation followed by a consolidation step, the tool is removed from the device. The separation of the process steps – injection and curing – has the advantage that a reversible deformation of the tooling during the filling process can be tolerated, which in turn allows the design of smaller wall thicknesses of the tool. This results in lighter and cheaper construction of tools.

The curing process can be done by a through-type furnace. In future applications the curing process may also be conducted by infrared radiation or a microwave applicator.

Fig. 6: Potential industrial process chain.

This filling technique should find its practice for both the prototype construction and mass

production. The separation of the filling and curing process may result in cost-efficient tooling investments. This is of special interest for mass production. The reason for using this novel injection method for prototype construction is that the overall equipment cost of this method may be competitive to traditional injection methods.

5.2 Feasibility study

a) Filling process: For an industrial use it has to be thought about an adapted position of this gate. The pin gate of the demonstrator is set conscious in the middle of the plate for the current demonstrator. Hence, the purpose is to investigate and understand the effects during the injection process. The use of several pin gates, a perforated sheet, etc. should be considered, too.

b) Size and geometry of composite parts: It has already been shown that smaller composite structures can be injected with the described process. It may be assumed that little curved structures are more facile to inject than the current specimen plate. The question is: Up to which geometrical size and shape of composite structures can the rotational injection be applied economically? Considerations for complex geometries including the complete manufacturing chain have to be included in the evaluation. It is supposable that the effort which has to be put in the process chain is not efficient for every part geometry (e.g. large parts).

4. Conclusion and outlook

In this first study the functionality and feasibility of the demonstrator is verified. It can be guaranteed that the preform can be fully impregnated with the method. The developed demonstrator produces reliable and reproducible plates made of GFRP and CFRP.

Two matrix systems are used. It is shown that the method enables the injection of high viscosity matrix systems.

The discussion reveals the integration of the injection process into the current process chain. In future studies a fundamental material characterization process will be conducted. The rates of porosities, the mechanical properties and the fiber volume content will be determined. The outgassing process will be investigated in detail. The rotational speed and the filling time are of special interest.

Acknowledgments

The authors would like to thank the SGL Group for supplying the carbon fibers, Saertex GmbH & Co. KG for supplying the glass fibers, SIKA GmbH and Momentive for supplying the matrix systems, the Institute for Carbon Composites (LCC) and the Institute of Medical and Polymer Engineering (Medtech) for providing production facilities. The authors gratefully acknowledge the support by the Faculty Graduate Center of Mechanical Engineering of TUM Graduate School at Technical University of Munich, Germany. The input of the LCC members helped to push forward the idea.

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